

Studies on Synthetic and Structural Aspects of Unsymmetrical Tetraorganoarsonium and stibonium Halides, Pseudohalides and Carboxylates : Electrophilic Cleavage of M-Allyl Bond

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Triphenylarsine and triphenylstibine react with allyl bromide to give the corresponding allyltriphenylarsonium and stibonium halides. The metal-allyl bond is readily cleaved by electrophiles, such as Br₂, I₂, ICl and IBr. Metathetical reactions involving allyltriphenylarsonium and stibonium halides and the appropriate metal salts, M'X (M' = Na, K, Ag; X = NCS, NCO, N₃, CH₃COO, CCl₃COO, C₆H₅COO) have been employed to yield a series of new compounds. The compounds are monomeric in benzene solution and 1 : 1 electrolyte in nitromethane.

Chatt and Mann¹ reported the first tetraphenylstibonium compound, Ph₄SbBr. Since then, a plethora of references describing the geometry and nature of the bonding and analytical applications of group-V organometallic pseudohalides and carboxylates, R_nMX_{5-n} (R = alkyl or aryl; M = As, Sb; X = pseudohalides and carboxylates; n = 3 or 4) have appeared in the literature²⁻⁵. The compounds are known to have ionic constitution^{6,7} and appeared to have 5-coordinate structures indicating a trigonal bipyramidal configuration around the group-V metal atom⁸. During the course of investigation of the oxidative addition reactions of triphenyl arsine and stibine [Ph₃M] with organohalides, RY [R = C₃H₅; Y = Br], a novel series of products RPh₃MY was obtained. It was considered worthwhile to employ these compounds to synthesise and to study further a series of allyltriphenylarsonium and stibonium derivatives, [Ph₃-C₃H₅MX], containing the anions (X = NCS, NCO, N₃, CH₃COO, C₆H₅COO, CCl₃COO), and examine the mode of bonding of these anions attached to the metal atom. Unsymmetrical allylarsonium and -stibonium compounds of these anions containing another organic moiety have not yet been reported. In view of the above background, the present work was undertaken to (i) prepare, Ph₃MRY (M = As, Sb; R = C₃H₅, Y = Br) and (ii) examine the mode of bonding of anionic group attached to metal atom (As, Sb) in RPh₃MX (R = C₃H₅; X = NCS, NCO, N₃, CH₃COO, C₆H₅COO, CCl₃COO), obtained through metathetical reactions involving metallic salts, M'X (M' = Na, K or Ag). Infrared spectra of the synthesised compounds have been reported herein. Also some solution studies have been discussed in the present work.

Results and Discussion

Organic halides have been reported to form tetraorganoarsonium and -stibonium derivatives^{6,7}. We have found that triphenylarsine and triphenylstibine when stirred in refluxing allylbromide (b.p. 70°) for 30 h, yielded allyltriphenylarsonium and allyltriphenylstibonium bromides in excellent yields

Cleavage of metal-allyl bond (M = As, Sb) : Subsequent cleavage of newly synthesised allyltriphenylarsonium bromide and allyltriphenylstibonium bromide have been studied. However, as compared to the cleavage of metal-phenyl and metal-allyl bonds in unsymmetrical tetraorganometallics with electrophilic reagents^{9,10}, there appears to be no report of the similar cleavage of arsenic-allyl and antimony-allyl bonds. In an earlier publication⁹, we demonstrated that the metal-allyl bond is cleaved in preference to the metal-phenyl bond by electrophilic reagents. This suggests that the M-C bond in the allyl derivatives is more reactive than in the metal-phenyl derivatives, and could be easily displaced even before the cleavage of the metal-phenyl bond, irrespective of nature of the electrophiles used. The metal-allyl bond in the allyltriphenylarsonium and allyltriphenylstibonium derivatives, however, is readily cleaved in preference to the oxidative reaction by electrophiles in accordance with equation (1). Since phenyl halides could not be detected, it is inferred that the metal-allyl bond is cleaved in preference to the metal-phenyl bond and also, it is suggested that the metal phenyl bonds are stable towards cleavage by the electrophilic reagents and consequently, metal-allyl bond breaks off,

where, M = As, Sb; YZ = I₂ or Br₂; Y = I; Z = Cl, Br.

It is thus evident that the cleavage of the allyl group in Ph₃M(C₃H₅)Br with Cl or Br stabilises the metal-halogen bond towards cleavage by ICl or IBr due to the greater electronegativity of Cl and Br and at the same time decreases the nucleophilicity of the metal-allyl bond through their electron-withdrawing power and only the metal-allyl bond is cleaved. Similar reactions of Ar₃SnX, Ar₃GeX and Ar₃PbX in which there is a further decrease in nucleophilicity of Ar-Sn bonds and the effect of change in the metal, have currently been studied¹¹.

We have observed in the present work that by using allyltriphenylarsonium and allyltriphenylstibonium derivatives, the metal-allyl cleavage preceded the metal-phenyl cleavage and being more favourable irrespective of the electrophiles used. The ease of electrophilic cleavage of such bond increases with the increase in the polarity of the bond. In this respect these iodine halides act as electrophilic reagents being polarised in the direction Y^+Z^- and attacking metal-allyl bond. A four-centered mechanism^{9,11} for similar reactions of group-IV compounds readily explains the formation of Ph_3MBrZ and allyl halides.

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS FOR THE UNSYMMETRICAL TETRAORGANOARSONIUM AND -STIBONIUM BROMIDES

Parameter	$Ph_3AsC_3H_5Br$	$Ph_3SbC_3H_5Br$
Yield (%)	80	90
M p ($^{\circ}C$)	205	192
Mol wt (in benzene)	426.00	475
Found/(Calcd)	(427.21)	(474.04)
Analysis (%)		
Found/(Calcd)		
C	59.42 (59.04)	52.60 (52.20)
H	4.92 (4.71)	4.36 (4.25)
Br	18.86 (18.70)	17.10 (16.86)
M	17.41 (17.53)	25.19 (25.68)

Metathetical reactions : Subsequently, metathetical reactions involving mixed allyltriphenylarsonium and -stibonium halides and the appropriate metal salts, $M'X$ ($M' = Na, K$ or Ag) have been carried out to replace selectively halides ions to yield a series of mixed allyltriphenylarsonium and -stibonium pseudohalides and carboxylates, $[Ph_3C_3H_5MX, M = As, Sb; X = NCS, NCO, N_3, CH_3COO, C_6H_5COO, CCl_3COO]$ according to the equation,

where, $M = As, Sb; Y = Br; M' = Na, K, Ag; X = NCO, NCS, N_3, CH_3COO, C_6H_5COO, CCl_3COO$. Products obtained in the reaction are crystalline, nonhygroscopic solids with sharp melting points which are soluble in organic solvent such as benzene, acetone, chloroform, carbon disulphide and are stable at room temperature. The molar conductance and relevant infrared assignments are listed in Table 3.

Molecular weight and conductance : The analytical and physical data of the compounds are recorded in Tables 1 and 3. The molecular weight data show that all the compounds exist as molecular and monomeric species in benzene. The electrical conductance data of these compounds (measured in nitromethane at 25° in the concentration range of 10^{-3} to $10^{-4} M$) have already been reported for tetraphenylarsonium and stibonium halides¹². Thus, the above compounds can be considered as 1 : 1 electrolyte in nitromethane.

Ir spectra : All pseudohalogen compounds have a strong ir active band in the $2300-2000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. The chalcogenates, NCX ($X = O, S, Se$) are capable of bonding to the metal either through N (iso) or X (normal). They give rise to three fundamental modes of vibration, the two of these correspond to asymmetric ($\nu_{C=N}$) and symmetric ($\nu_{C=X}$) stretching of the functional group and a third one being the bending band. The vibrations associated with the asymmetric stretching of the isocyanate (NCO) and isothiocyanate (NCS) were also observed at $2200-2180$ and $2060-2040\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. These vibrations are in good agreement with those reported for other organometallic pseudohalides^{3,4}. The nature of the cyanate and the thiocyanate derivatives is better elucidated by the δNCX [$X = O$ or S] bending modes, which lie at ~ 640 and $\sim 480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, indicating that both the cyanate and the thiocyanate groups are involved in bonding through the nitrogen atom to give an isostructure^{3-5,13}. The band at 2040 cm^{-1} ($N=N=N$ asymmetric stretching) is the strongest in all spectra of the azide group in these compounds which is in conformity with the earlier findings^{14,15}. The band is close to that observed in covalent organic azides¹⁵, but shifted to higher frequencies as compared to

TABLE 2—CLEAVAGE REACTIONS OF ALLYLTRIPHENYLARSONIUM AND -STIBONIUM BROMIDES WITH ELECTROPHILES

Reactants	Molar ratio	Time(h)/ (Temp, $^{\circ}C$)	Product	M p/(Lit) $^{\circ}C$	Yield %
$Ph_3AsC_3H_5Br + I_2$	1 : 1	4 (25)	Ph_3AsIBr	154 (155) ^a	80
$Ph_3AsC_3H_5Br + Br_2$	1 : 1	2 (0)	Ph_3AsBr_2	215 (215) ^a	86
$Ph_3AsC_3H_5Br + ICl$	1 : 1	2 (0)	$Ph_3AsBrCl$	170 ^b	84
$Ph_3AsC_3H_5Br + IBr$	1 : 1	3 (25)	Ph_3AsBr_2	215 (215) ^a	86
$Ph_3SbC_3H_5Br + I_2$	1 : 1	4 (25)	Ph_3SbIBr	214 (215) ^c	90
$Ph_3SbC_3H_5Br + Br_2$	1 : 1	1 (0)	Ph_3SbBr_2	216 (216) ^c	88
$Ph_3SbC_3H_5Br + ICl$	1 : 1	2 (0)	$Ph_3SbBrCl$	230 ^d	84
$Ph_3SbC_3H_5Br + IBr$	1 : 1	2 (25)	Ph_3SbBr_2	216 (216) ^c	80

^aRef 22 ^bFound C, 50.68, H, 3.72 Calcd for C, 51.28, H, 3.58% ^cRef 26 ^dFound C, 45.92, H, 3.02 Calcd for C, 46.15, H, 3.23

TABLE 3—EXCHANGE REACTIONS OF $\text{Ph}_3\text{MC}_3\text{H}_5\text{Br}$ WITH K, Na AND Ag SALTS ($\text{M}'\text{X}$) (1 : 1)

M	$\text{Ph}_3\text{MC}_3\text{H}_5\text{X}$	M.p. °C	Mol.wt. Found/(calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
				C	H	N	S/Cl	M
As	NCO	110	389.16	67.80	5.10	3.61	—	19.38
			(389.32)	67.87	5.17	3.59	—	19.24
As	NCS	90	404.68	64.52	4.36	3.60	7.80	18.21
			(405.38)	65.18	4.97	3.45	7.90	18.48
As	N_3	155	388.46	63.82	4.98	10.68	—	19.20
			(389.33)	64.78	5.17	10.79	—	19.24
As	CH_3COO	103	406.06	67.02	5.40	—	—	18.01
			(406.35)	67.98	5.70	—	—	18.43
As	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}$	95	468.34	71.69	5.40	—	—	15.01
			(468.42)	71.79	5.37	—	—	15.99
As	CCl_3COO	112	508.87	53.40	4.96	—	20.10	14.06
			(509.69)	53.20	3.95	—	20.86	14.69
Sb	NCO	216	436.06	60.10	4.14	3.01	—	27.02
			(436.15)	60.58	4.62	3.21	—	27.91
Sb	NCS	240	451.34	58.01	4.40	4.08	7.16	26.81
			(452.21)	58.43	4.45	3.09	7.08	26.92
Sb	N_3	170	435.22	57.12	4.71	9.01	—	27.06
			(436.15)	57.83	4.62	9.63	—	27.91
Sb	CH_3COO	116	452.26	61.06	5.10	—	—	26.01
			(453.18)	60.95	5.11	—	—	26.86
Sb	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}$	101	514.60	65.02	4.01	—	—	23.41
			(515.25)	65.27	4.89	—	—	23.62
Sb	CCl_3COO	130	556.20	49.50	3.40	—	20.22	21.75
			(556.51)	49.63	3.62	—	19.11	21.87

ionic azides^{14,16}. The second band of much lower intensity ($\sim 1330\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is assigned to an overtone of the $\text{N}=\text{N}=\text{N}$ bending mode, the fundamental³ of which appear at $\sim 640 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These observations were coupled with the high solubility of the compounds in organic solvents, and their low melting points suggest a predominately covalent character for the newly synthesised azide compounds. The bands associated with the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxylate group occur at 1633 ± 5 and $1330 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. In the solid state the carboxylate stretching frequencies are of the same order as reported for the free acetate ion or bidentate carboxylate ligand¹⁷. However, carboxylate stretching frequencies in solution are expected for a monodentate acetate group¹⁷. It has been shown that the separation between $\nu_{\text{asym}}\text{COO}$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}\text{COO}$ is smaller (160 cm^{-1}) for monomeric compound¹⁷. Since the separation observed in the present investigation is fairly large, a monomolecular structure containing pentacoordinated metal (As, Sb) is suggested with a monodentate carboxylate^{18–20}. Regarding the vibrations associated with the metal-carbon bond stretchings ($\text{M}-\text{C}$, $\sim 400\text{ cm}^{-1}$), no definite assignment could be made due to the presence of the phenyl absorption band in the region $300\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. A study²¹ of vibrational spectra of triphenyl compounds of the main group-V elements indicates that metal-carbon stretching vibrations occur below 400 cm^{-1} . However, due to the overlap with the phenyl ring

vibrations the assignments can not be made unequivocally. Absorption frequencies due to the metal-ligand (Cl, Br, I) stretching vibrations could not be identified in any compound. The frequencies are most likely to occur near 300 cm^{-1} or lower and again due to the presence of phenyl bands no conclusion can be reached about them. To conclude the results of study, the compounds are monomeric in freezing benzene as 1 : 1 electrolyte in nitromethane. With the exception of the acetate, all the compounds appear to have a 5-coordinate structure in the solid state. The acetate appears to have a 6-coordinate structure in the solid state, but a 5-coordinate structure in the solution. The reason for this difference in the mode of coordination of the acetate group is not clear at present and is in accordance with the reported²² differences in the properties of the tertiary organometallic dihalides, R_3MY_2 (R = methyl or phenyl; M = Group-VB atom; Y = halides) of the group-VB elements.

Experimental

Triphenylarsine²³ and triphenylstibine²⁴ were prepared through Wurtz reaction, and had the reported melting points. Iodine monochloride (Fluka) was distilled before use. Iodine monobromide was prepared by the published method^{9,10}. Iodine (E. Merck) was resublimed before use. Freshly prepared silver salts were dried under reduced pressure while alkali salts (A.R.) were used as such. Anhydrous chloroform and carbon tetrachloride were used as

solvent. Moisture was excluded wherever necessary.

Reaction of triphenylarsine with allylbromide : Triphenylarsine (1.08 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in allylbromide (5 ml) was heated at 70° for 42 h and allowed to stand overnight. The colourless crystals which separated out on the addition of ether was filtered after keeping them in ether for 24 h.

Cleavage of allyltriphenylstibonium bromide by iodine : To a stirred solution of allyltriphenylstibonium bromide (4.91 g, 0.01 mol) in chloroform (50 ml) was added dropwise a solution of iodine (2.76 g, 0.01 mol) in the same solvent (30 ml). The violet colour of iodine disappeared after each addition. After the complete addition, the solution was further stirred for 30 min to ensure the completion of the reaction. The solvent was then removed and the residue distilled to give allyliodide (1.34 g, 80%), b.p. 102° (lit.²⁵ 102°/74 mm). The residue was recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to give triphenylantimony bromide iodide (5.60 g, 0.01 mol), m.p. 214° (lit.²⁶ 215°).

A similar experiment with allyltriphenylarsonium bromide gave triphenylarsenic bromideiodide in 86% yield.

Reaction of Ph₃MRY with M'X (X = pseudohalide and carboxylate) : Allyltriphenylarsonium and -stibonium halides were added to a suspension of an excess of freshly prepared anhydrous M'X (M' = Na, K, Ag; X = NCS, NCO, N₃, CH₃COO, C₆H₅COO, CCl₃COO) in dry CHCl₃ (100 ml). The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 24 h. A yellow precipitate of metal bromide separated out. The solution was filtered and the solvent distilled off to give a residue which was crystallised from petroleum ether (60–80%).

C, H and N analyses were obtained from C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Halide ions were estimated gravimetrically by precipitating out with AgNO₃ as AgCl. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Molecular weight was determined in benzene. Conductance measurements were made on 10⁻³ M solutions of the complex in nitromethane using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge.

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